

PECULIAR FEATURES OF MEDIA-DISOURSE AS A LINGUISTIC DISCOURSE TYPE

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Abstract:

This thesis deals with one of the most important discourse types; that is media-discourse. Characteristic features of media-discourse, communicative and informative functions, linguistic issues related to mass-media are also studied in the thesis. As English media-discourse has covered nearly all spheres of life throughout the world specific aspects of this media is analyzed in the work.

Key words: applied linguistics, linguistic unit, media-streams, content-based information, publicity, cognitive intention, stage of perception.

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The term “discourse” is analyzed differently by various scientists. Many previous studies mention the term discourse as very ambiguous since its introduction to modern science and the various broad interpretations of discourse. Therefore, the definition of discourse reflected here will focus on the linguistics point of view, especially that of applied linguistics. Here, it refers to the speech patterns and how language, dialects, and acceptable statements are used in a particular community. Discourse as a subject of study looks at discourse among people who share the same speech conventions. Discourse in modern linguistics regarded as a linguistic unit - a unit of language that is longer than a sentence, such as a conversation or story, as a form of communication - a verbal exchange of ideas, often interactive, that deals with a particular topic, as a formal expression - a formal and orderly expression of thought on a subject, often extended. In sociology, discourse can have powerful implications and is often the site of conflict and struggle. For example, how people talk about people and their place in society can be important when people wish to make social change. Discourse is widely used in all scientific approaches today. One of the most important types of discourse in general is media-discourse. At present time media-discourse has become a very important discourse.

The second half of the XX – the beginning of the XXI century is characterized by the rapid growth of media and new information technologies. The dynamic development of traditional media and spread of the Internet has contributed to the formation of a single information space, conglomeration of many media-streams. The Internet and related technologies are categorized as a leading mass communication and essential information resource processing and distributing large data arrays. As a result media greatly affects communicant language behaviour.

Prof. Dobrosklonskaya views media discourse as a set of processes and products of language activities in mass communication sphere in all diversity and complexity of their interactions [Dobrosklonskaya, 2018, pp. 131-139]. As a special type of mass communication media discourse is a social phenomenon, whose main function is to influence mass audience through content-based information and evaluative data transmitted by media channels. Consequently media discourse is a mechanism of updating information through different communication tools of Media Institute. I.A. Kozhemyakin distinguishes two approaches to

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the definition of media discourse. The first approach postulates that media discourse is a specific verbal-mental activity, peculiar only for information mass media space [Montgomery, Kostomarov, Dobrosklonskaya, 2019, pp.27- 40]. This approach differentiates media discourse from other discourse types such as political, religious, scientific, etc. on the basis of such discourse parameters as the use of language and communicative sphere of its realization. The second approach states that media discourse is any kind of discourse realized in media space and produced by mass media. Thus it is possible to distinguish political, religious, scientific media discourse characterized by the specificity of mass information formation, interpretation and broadcasting.

M.R. Zheltuhina defines distinctive features of media discourse that include - group correlation (the author shares the views of his group); - publicity (focusing on mass addressee); - disens orientation (creating conflict with its following discussion); - staging and mass orientation (impact on several groups simultaneously) [Zheltuhina, Magomadova, 2016; pp.120-121].

The media discourse in the information space of the university implements informative and representative functions and has a significant impact on the image of the university both in the academic and scientific environment, and in society as a whole. The purpose of the media discourse analysis is to describe them image of an educational institution, which is attractive to students, scientists, the business environment, and the dissemination of innovations in education and science. Media discourse is a certain kind of speaking and thinking that is unique to the media area of information. In this view, it is important to make a distinction between media discourse and other sorts of discourse that are not related to the media, including political, religious, scientific, etc. Modifications to the discourse parameters, as well as various language usage patterns and the contexts in which they are used, determine their differences. According to the second method, by media discourse is meant any kind of discourse that is used in mass communication and is created by the media. Yes, we can discuss media discourses that are pedagogical, religious, political, or otherwise. It is acknowledged that a fairly consistent set of practices for the creation, dissemination, and interpretation of mass information are necessary for the execution of various kinds of institutional discourse. Since media discourse is an activity carried out by subjects of mass communication, it is driven by a particular goal, in accordance with which it obtains a particular content. Description and explanation, addressee identity regulation, recipient consciousness impact, reality evaluation, scenario forecasting, etc. are all potential goals of media discourse.

Each mass media discourse has got a specific intention. Cognitive intention determines the addressee's role and communicative intention realizes the author's potential. Interactivity does not imply a clear separation between the addressee and addresser, which is observed in natural communication. Communicative intention is inherent in the author of the message. Being implemented in media discourse, communicative intention provides the author with the status of the subject of constructing media reality and is one of the important parameters of the segmentation of the addressee field. Depending on the communicative intention, two types of addressees are distinguished in the address field, i.e. repeaters and non-repeaters. Repeaters are involved in the construction of the media reality. Professional and non-professional repeaters, as well as institutional entities, stand out in this segment. The first ones are journalists who are recipients of objective reality and recipients of media reality and transmit information further to the addressee field. Unprofessional repeaters are citizen journalists that create their own content and interpret previous messages. The third subgroup includes social groups that have gained access to a mass audience and are interested in saturating the mass consciousness with the "right" news. The intension of non-translators does not imply their verbal reactivity in the media discourse. In this segment of the address field, there have been selected positive recipients that are configured for a productive

perception of media content in order to obtain certain information and negative recipients with their prejudice that inhibits the selection of facts at the stage of perception and, therefore, the adaptation of the world picture to a changing reality [Prom, 2020; pp.3-7].

At present time English has become the language of many spheres of life throughout the world. It is also the language of diplomacy. The language that is often used in media-discourse worldwide is English as well. Modern English-language media discourse is a complex integral phenomenon, “a huge layer of culture” not only for the English-speaking society, but also for the entire world community, taking into account the role that English plays as a means of global communication, or “lingua franca”. English-language media discourse is a global leading mediator for almost all spheres of social life on the planet. Political and economic models, scientific breakthrough discoveries, international academic programs, the world of sports, showbusiness and fashion are all circulated and processed in the English-language media discourse space; they are filtered by its unique features and presented to the international audience as an effective tool of communication, influence and exposure. One can observe the English-language media discourse as a role model for the media world, represented in other languages. Even within the English-language media discourse itself, there is the stiff competition which depends on each English-speaking country dominance on a global political, economic and military scale. English-language media discourse is important both for what it tells people about an Englishspeaking and non-speaking society in a particular country and for what it contributes to the character of this society. Therefore, it is important to understand the relationship between an individual (both a native English speaker and a non-native one) and the English-language media discourse space, between human consciousness and its mechanisms which interact with the media discourse and produce actions that may influence a person's worldview, his behaviour, personal life, social status, beliefs and destiny. The English-language media discourse is playing a dominant role in the modern digital civilization. Its influence goes far beyond the English-speaking world and in many political, economic, scientific and social ways defines the lives of peoples on the planet. Therefore, the questions which logically appear in this case is how human consciousness should resist to such rigorous expansion of the English-speaking media world dominance and how psychological mechanisms should function while interacting with this world to protect each person's uniqueness and freedom on a global scale.

Besides, mass-media is very active in the formation of neologisms, and, because of its constant development and actual nature, its efficiency will develop. Through mass communication, people configure and substantiate their own beliefs and experiences. Mass media is predetermined not only by information awareness but also by daily life and the picture of the world. Mass communication can be considered the space where people create and share life experience, values and knowledge. Being nationally specific, neologisms through their space realize those categories that are thought by representatives of a particular people, and the limitations into which they are put to perceive and analyze the world around them.

Media-discourse materials can serve as an important methodological basis for English teaching and learning process as well. Considering these facts teachers, instructors may use media discourse widely in their classes. This is an authentic material containing essential news happening in all world corners, besides, the modern language units are included in these materials. Taking into account these issues there are still huge demands to study and analyze media-discourse and materials in it.

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